
101. The nearest black hole

GAIA IS ENABLING the discovery of two important classes of stellar-mass black holes in our Galaxy: *isolated* black holes, and those in binary systems which lack significant mass transfer. Amongst the latter, recently reported, is the nearest known black hole, at just 480 pc. I will start with a ‘big picture’ for background.

A BLACK HOLE is a region of spacetime where gravity is so strong that nothing, neither particles nor electromagnetic radiation (including light), can escape. Since the work of Karl Schwarzschild in 1916, black holes were known to be consistent with the theory of general relativity. But they were viewed more as a mathematical curiosity, at least until the discovery of neutron stars in 1967 stimulated interest in gravitationally collapsed compact objects as a possible astrophysical reality.

The first observational evidence for a black hole was Cygnus X-1, a high-mass X-ray binary discovered in 1964, and characterised (from the 1970s) as comprising a blue supergiant orbiting a $20M_{\odot}$ black hole at about 0.2 au. A stellar wind from the supergiant provides material which forms a hot accretion disk around the black hole, generating the observed X-rays. And the compact object is considered too small to be anything other than a black hole. Gaia DR3, incidentally, pinpoints Cygnus X-1 at 2250 ± 80 pc (0.4439 ± 0.0149 mas).

IN THE 50 years since, stellar-mass black holes have been inferred to exist in some 20 of the 300 or so (low-mass and high-mass) X-ray binaries now known in our Galaxy. With masses spanning $5 - 20M_{\odot}$ or more, they are thought to have formed by gravitational stellar collapse, often accompanied by a gamma-ray burst. The Hipparcos Catalogue, by the way, included just eight of the then-known high-mass X-ray binary systems.

Despite this small number of suspected stellar-mass black holes, there are held to be many millions throughout our Galaxy. But if they exist in wider-separation binaries, there will be little or no accreting matter to signal their presence through high-energy radiation. And those that are isolated, perhaps the majority, could only be discovered through gravitational lensing.

I SHOULD MENTION, for completeness, although they are not part of this story, that there are also ‘super-massive’ black holes, weighing in at *millions* of solar masses, which are believed to exist in the centres of most galaxies, including our own. They are believed to grow through the accretion of other stars or, over cosmological epochs, by mergers with other black holes; in February 2016, the LIGO–Virgo collaboration announced the first direct detection of gravitational waves, representing the first observation of a black hole merger.

RETURNING TO stellar-mass black holes, the mass distribution of the X-ray binary candidates is tantalising: it peaks around $7 - 8M_{\odot}$, with few if any below $5M_{\odot}$. This suggests that a ‘mass gap’ exists between the highest measured masses of neutron stars in binary radio pulsars, of around $2.1 - 2.3M_{\odot}$, and the lowest-mass black holes (e.g. Sahu et al., 2022).

The mass distribution falls off above $10M_{\odot}$, and few (X-ray binary) black hole masses are known above about $15M_{\odot}$. Indeed, the only known exception in our Galaxy is the latest mass determination, from VLBA as well as Gaia EDR3 astrometry, for the black hole in Cygnus X-1, of $21.1 \pm 2.2M_{\odot}$ (Miller-Jones et al., 2021).

More information on black hole masses is therefore of great interest. And there are two ‘classes’ of occurrences for which Gaia is contributing.

THE FIRST is through ongoing microlensing searches. This approach is important because of the evidence suggesting that a substantial fraction of stellar-mass black holes are single. And in consequence, being less affected by binary interactions, isolated black holes may provide a more direct probe of their formation.

Isolated black holes are, as I mentioned above, extremely difficult to detect directly, with microlensing offering the only current discovery method, and with no convincing candidates known pre-Gaia.

But ‘normal’ microlensing alone is insufficient: the well-known degeneracy between lens mass and lens-source relative velocity can only be resolved if accurate *astrometry* accompanies the photometry (essay #11).

In a 100-author paper by members of the OGLE, MOA, PLANET, μ FUN, MiNDSTeP, and RoboNet microlensing teams, Sahu et al. (2022) observed the 2011 microlensing event MOA-2011-BLG-191 (also known as OGLE-2011-BLG-0462) with the Hubble Space Telescope at eight epochs over six years.

They measured an astrometric deflection of the background star's apparent position, which together with the parallactic signature of the Earth's motion on the microlensing light curve, led to a lens mass of $7.1 \pm 1.3 M_{\odot}$, and a distance of 1.58 ± 0.18 kpc. Gaia EDR3 astrometry enabled the measurement of the astrometric deflection by providing the proper motions of the background stars in the HST images during the 6-yr of observations to properly characterise the reference frame.

Finding that the lens itself emits no detectable light, and with a lens mass higher than that of a white dwarf or neutron star, they confirmed its black hole nature. Their mass measurement is, they emphasise, the first for an isolated stellar-mass black hole using any technique.

Their astrometry also provides an absolute proper motion for the black hole. Being offset from the mean motion of Galactic disk stars at similar distances by a transverse space velocity of 45 km s^{-1} , furthermore suggests that it received a 'natal kick' during the supernova explosion that led to its formation.

THE SECOND class for which Gaia is contributing, and somewhat more decisively, is in the case of non-accreting (or weakly accreting) black hole binaries. Some have recently been discovered in longer-period spectroscopic binaries, occupying the neutron star/black hole 'gap' with masses of $3 - 4.5 M_{\odot}$.

In parallel, the substantial nearby binary star population being discovered and characterised through Gaia astrometry has demonstrated the possibility of detecting many more wide binary systems containing quiescent black holes, with masses for some hundred or more in prospect (e.g. Chawla et al. 2022; Janssens et al. 2022).

Indeed, Gaia DR3 already includes orbital solutions for more than 100 000 single-lined spectroscopic binaries, more than a factor 10 in sample size compared with all previous studies, and for which accretor masses can probably be derived (El-Badry et al., 2022).

AMONGST THIS potential future haul, and using the binary catalogue included as part of Gaia Data Release 3, two papers have independently reported the discovery of the first such binary system, the $G = 13.8$ mag Gaia DR3 4373465352415301632, comprising a main-sequence sun-like star and a massive *non-interacting* black hole candidate (Chakrabarti et al. 2022; El-Badry et al. 2022).

Selected for more careful study on the basis of its high mass ratio, and its location close to the main

sequence, follow-up spectroscopy and radial velocity monitoring of this system validated and refined the Gaia orbit solution.

The spectral energy distribution of the visible star is well described by a single star model (a slowly-rotating G dwarf with $T_{\text{eff}} = 5900 \text{ K}$, $\log(g) = 4.5$, $M_1 = 0.9 M_{\odot}$). Importantly, no contribution from another luminous source is required to fit the observed photometry. Joint modeling of the radial velocities and astrometry constrains the companion (black hole) mass to $M_2 = 9.8 \pm 0.2 M_{\odot}$.

Other noteworthy properties are that the main-sequence star is at most only moderately metal-poor, $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}] = -0.30$. And it is on a Galactic orbit similar to thin disk stars, suggesting that it formed in the Milky Way disk with at most a weak natal kick.

Both papers conclude that this binary system harbours a massive black hole on an eccentric ($e = 0.45 \pm 0.02$), long-period ($185.4 \pm 0.1 \text{ d}$) orbit, much longer than the typical black hole X-ray binaries discovered to date. And at a distance of only 480 pc, it is the nearest known black hole by a factor of 3. Its discovery hints at the existence of a sizeable population of 'dormant' black holes in binary star systems.

El-Badry et al. (2022) argue that explaining the system's formation with standard binary evolutionary models is challenging. Specifically, it is not clear how the luminous star would survive a common envelope event under standard assumptions, and difficult for it to end up in a wide orbit afterwards. They conclude that formation models involving a triple system, or dynamical assembly in an open cluster, may be more plausible.

THE DISCOVERY OF black holes around luminous stars from their measured orbital accelerations now provides a new avenue for understanding the different possible formation channels of black holes in our Galaxy.

With estimates suggesting that there are perhaps a million similar systems in the Milky Way, future Gaia data releases may discover upwards of a hundred.

El-Badry et al. (2022)

Chakrabarti et al. (2022)